

WALK BEFORE WE RUN: THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION JOURNEY AT THE UNIVERSITY OF OTAGO LIBRARY

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Abstract – The University of Otago Library Te Pātaka Mātauraka o Ōtākou Whakaihu Waka, needed to replace its digital asset management system which failed to deliver on both digital preservation and collection access goals. The University initiated a project prioritising ‘preservation for access’ to migrate approximately 18,000 digital collection items, integrate with existing collection management systems and establish digital preservation and discovery workflows.

Despite several obstacles, collaboration between the Hocken Collections, the Library, and Information Technology Services improved digital preservation understanding for the organisation and helped ensure access to digital collection items in perpetuity.

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I. INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

The Hocken Collections Uare Taoka o Hākena is a research library, archive and gallery contained within the University of Otago Library, Te Pātaka Mātauraka o Ōtākou Whakaihu Waka.

The Hocken Collections contain archives, manuscripts, books, drawings, journals, maps, music, film, newspapers, artwork and ephemera dating from the 17th Century to today. The Collections ‘celebrate the histories, cultures and

natural environments of Aotearoa New Zealand, the Pacific and Antarctica with special emphasis on southern New Zealand’ [1].

The Hocken has provided digitisation services to researchers for many years to assist with remote access and safe handling of collection items, as well as providing high-quality digitisation for publications. To help manage the increasing number of digital items, a project was launched in 2015 to implement a digital asset management system. The result – colloquially known as ‘the DAMS’ – was launched in 2016.

The DAMS was built atop Islandora [2], an open-source system that used several in-house customisations to allow integration with both the unpublished and published collection management systems, as well other customisations to support the digitisation workflows of the time. Whilst this platform provided the ability to digitally preserve and make digital collection items accessible to the public, neither aspect was ever fully realised due to technical challenges and Library priorities.

In 2017, the University of Otago underwent a structural centralisation that shifted digital teams formerly within the Library into the University’s Information Technology Services (ITS) division; in the intervening time, several key staff members in the Library moved on, leaving knowledge gaps.

The Library understood that much like how established preservation and conservation techniques allow today's researchers to access physical works of knowledge created centuries ago, digital preservation allows tomorrow's researchers (who may not have been born yet) to access these digital works of knowledge.

II. THE PROJECT

As the Library's digitised and born-digital collections have grown and will continue to do so, in late 2021 the University Library partnered with ITS to identify a suitable replacement for DAMS as it did not deliver the Library's requirements. This investigation was also driven by a need to migrate away from Islandora as ITS faced sustainability and security issues with some of the underlying technologies. After a market scan in light of the Library's requirements, a procurement process took place and Clarivate's Rosetta digital preservation product was selected.

All parties involved understood that whilst there are technical aspects to digital preservation, implementing a digital preservation service is not a purely technical exercise. A great deal of work requiring intellectual effort and rigour comes before a digital object comes anywhere near a preservation system. After a digital object is ingested, more effort and rigour are required to understand the preservation risks involved and how to mitigate them. There's also ongoing thought around discovery and delivery, future collections, policy, advocacy and other non-technical sides to the work.

An implementation project was formed at the beginning of 2024, with the team consisting of staff from the Hocken, the Library, ITS (notably, the Library Systems team) and the vendor. Hocken and Library staff provided the knowledge of collections, metadata and current digitisation workflows to help design the future state; ITS and the vendor provided the technical knowledge to help achieve that future state. This collaborative approach would deliver the best outcomes and is reflected in the University of Otago Library Strategy 2023-2028 [3], specifically the Strategic Themes of *Partnering for success* and *Amplifying research*.

Guided by a high-level goal of 'Preservation for access', the project aimed to deliver:

- Migration of around 18,000 digital collection items and their metadata from the DAMS into Rosetta;
- Identification of other digital collection items and their metadata held in other systems to migrate into Rosetta;
- Integration between Rosetta and both the published and unpublished collection management systems so that metadata may be synchronised;
- Application and technical workflow development for ingesting digital collection items (both born-digital and digitised), both as individual items and in bulk;
- Creation of a minimum level of appropriate discovery, delivery and access to digital collection items within Rosetta through both the Library's discovery service (Library Search | Ketu) and the web-facing search for the unpublished collections management system (Hākena).

III. CHOPPRTUNITIES (CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES)

A. *Project engagement with Tangata Whenua*

The University Library has always had good engagement with the local runaka (tribal council) as many collection items are Taoka Māori – cultural treasures representing Mātauraka Māori (knowledge) and Te Ao Māori (worldview). The Library acts as kaitiaki (guardian) of these collection items instead of as an 'owner'; as such, a collective understanding with the traditional knowledge holders on care and access is vital.

Near the end of the project some team members felt that consultation was needed with the runaka before the digital Taoka Māori could be made available publicly. Since the runaka had previously agreed to make the digital Taoka available in the context of other digitisation projects, there was an assumption that there was implicit permission to do so again.

The project paused so the Library could consult with the runaka on the project and its expected outcomes.

This helped highlight the Library's responsibility for active ongoing collaborative agreement with Tangata Whenua. This helps future projects avoid miscommunication and assumption, as well as strengthening cultural reciprocity.

B. Institutional Knowledge

A major challenge for the project was a lack of in-depth knowledge about the ongoing work of digital preservation, as Library staff who may have been able to help guide direction of the project had since left the organisation.

One of the Library Systems team members had experience with digital preservation in previous collecting institutions, so was able to share background and information to the project team on theories, standards and practicalities of digital preservation from both collections [4] and technology [5] standpoints.

Learning all the aspects of digital preservation provided a steep learning curve for the rest of the project team.

The vendor was very helpful when we had configuration questions, though at some points the questions were met with 'it depends on how you want to do things'. Since digital preservation wasn't yet baked into the organisation, the team didn't know the right path to take and had to make a best guess to proceed. The feeling of 'we don't know what we don't know' led to some false starts. Having more business-driven discussions with other organisations about digital preservation before the project started would have been helpful to better guide the decisions.

From this we learnt not to underestimate the basic understanding required to properly implement a digital preservation service. Whilst not necessarily requiring end-to-end expertise, there needs to be a firm organisational grounding in the 'what' and 'why' of digital preservation, if not the 'how'. The risk is spending significant time upskilling staff during the course of the project.

Digital preservation knowledge is still growing for the Library, but as more staff become aware of what digital preservation is and why it's vital for a 21st Century cultural heritage organisation, the tenor of queries and conversation in this space has become more proactive as we move forward.

C. Personnel

Since the Library lacked a dedicated role to manage digital preservation, a contractor was initially brought in to document the Library's local digital collection workflows, as well as to help bridge the gap for some of the non-technical aspects which would help with designing the future state.

The approach of using a contractor in this role was seen as a short-term solution until a permanent staff member could be appointed; however, after several months, this contract ended and the project had not yet finished. At this point ITS provided a Business Analyst to assist, but their focus was more on documenting workflows rather than understanding the digital preservation aspects and their potential future impacts.

The Library has since made a successful case to the University that a role to manage digital preservation is necessary. The case was made by outlining the risk to digitised and born-digital collections, as well as the benefit to making these collections more discoverable and accessible.

Digital preservation requires a dedicated role or roles. Broadly speaking, digital preservation comprises advocacy, policy, communication, quality assurance, collection understanding, metadata understanding and technical understanding. It's not something that can be encapsulated under the 'other duties as required' line in a role description.

As of this writing the role has not been filled. In the meantime, the collaborative approach between the Library and Library Systems shapes the direction of the service.

D. Bringing people along on the journey

Implementing a new way of doing things supported by a new tool is a challenge in any organisation. In this project, the challenge is best illustrated by the two phrases 'this is the way it's always been done' and 'the 100% problem'.

To work through the first challenge, reminding people of the benefits for researchers helped. Long-term digital preservation of the collection items would allow future researchers access to the collections; present-day researchers would benefit by gaining access to thousands of collection items that had been digitised but were not available.

The second challenge - where some wanted to deliver a 100% perfect solution before going live - had to be addressed in a practical way. Not only would the '100% approach' have added scope creep

to the project, it would also not be technically achievable with the resources available. Luckily, continuous improvement philosophy and processes already existed between the Library and ITS and this allowed everyone to understand that even though the project would finish, the work would continue.

E. Workflows

During the project it became clear that few of the extant processes around local digital collection development and management were documented and standardised across the organisation. This meant things like processes to handle researcher and other digitisation requests, digitisation workflows/techniques, metadata creation, access permissions assignment and preservation standards varied.

This impacted the project at times, as it meant consideration of different approaches depending on collection content and past, undocumented, decisions. The project team discussed each of these to determine a consensus approach, and whilst these discussions were sometimes robust, we needed to have a shared understanding if the project were to succeed.

These discussions led to some internal review of processes and standards to improve and document them. Work has also begun at a higher level between the Library and the University Continuous Improvement team to create consistent standards for future digitisation efforts, including what metadata is required.

Documentation and standardisation are your friends; without these a digital preservation service is not sustainable. This can be approached in an iterative (and retrospective) manner rather than having everything done before progressing. However, this requires the organisational will to go through the process and to revisit it when necessary.

F. Metadata

One aspect of the project that required deep discussion and understanding is how archival description – specifically, the ISAD(G)-based description used at the Hocken – doesn't neatly work in a digital context.

In the digital realm, often the metadata has a one-to-one relationship with the item. However, archival descriptive practice uses nested hierarchies of metadata and individual items may be described minimally. (The artworks in the Hocken Collection did

not face this challenge, as they have a one-item-to-one-description relationship.)

A particular archival item like a photograph may have a description like 'Group photograph of students', but more context is provided by the container in which that item is found ('Photographs 1931-1940'), which itself is in turn held in a container ('University of Otago photographs and clippings used on display boards (1911-1986)'). The hierarchy could be several more layers deep.

Whilst the hierarchical approach is necessary for describing the physical archival collections, it made metadata assignment for the digital representations challenging. As items were migrated there was no way to walk 'up' the hierarchy to collate the metadata and apply it to a single digital collection item.

This concerned some project team members, as they believed that digital collection items discovered in Library Search | Ketu (the Library's discovery service) wouldn't appear to be well-described.

A compromise was reached so that part of the Rosetta metadata contained a link to the item's source within Hākena (the discovery service for unpublished Hocken Collections) so that the hierarchy of the item could still be navigated and understood.

This mirrors how other institutions have approached the same issue, and whilst not a perfect solution, a mass retrospective item-level descriptive programme was not an option. What metadata displays and how it displays for preserved collection items will be an ongoing consideration for the Library.

Flexibility about how and where metadata is surfaced to your communities is key. Communication and compromise are key here to make digitally-preserved collections accessible. If possible, link back to the 'source of truth' for descriptive metadata. Think longer-term about discovery and delivery, and how hierarchical metadata could better be represented.

G. System integrations

When items were added to the DAMS, they used the descriptive metadata held in the Hocken's unpublished collection management system (UCMS). Due to numerous technical challenges between the two systems, this description remained within the DAMS as it was when first deposited, as there was no way to automate updates from the UCMS into the DAMS.

As part of ingesting the digital collection items into Rosetta, the project team decided to refresh this metadata from the UCMS at time of ingest. This used the OAI-PMH [6] feed from the UCMS to retrieve the metadata; the intent was to use the same mechanism to provide updated metadata into Rosetta on an ongoing basis.

Unfortunately, it was discovered that the OAI-PMH implementation within the UCMS did not follow the OAI-PMH standard, so there was no way to utilise this. A request was made to the UCMS vendor to address this; at the time of writing, this remains an issue.

The project team also planned that after a digital collection item was ingested into Rosetta, the collection item record in the UCMS would be updated with a link to the Rosetta viewer, so that researchers and staff could access the digital representation.

Other than manually opening each UCMS record and adding the link, there was no apparent way to do this. The UCMS vendor was asked if there were any application programming interfaces (API) available that could do this, but there were not. The vendor then went away to create an API to address this, and several months later it was provided. However, this solution was deemed unsuitable due to lack of security and its bespoke nature – it seemed that the API was only added to the Hocken UCMS instance rather than incorporated fully into the product.

The Library Systems team then devised a way to extract the viewer links from Rosetta then bulk-load them into the UCMS, far from an automated process.

The lack of sustainable systemic integration both to and from the UCMS has made both the Library and ITS realise that requirements for what the Library needs from a modern unpublished collection management system need to be developed. That work will begin later in 2025.

If systems can't be properly integrated, it's time to consider new systems. Short-term workarounds may be possible but shouldn't be considered a sustainable practice.

IV. OUTCOMES AND NEXT STEPS

In November 2024, migration into Rosetta had completed, and 18,000 digital collection items were being digitally preserved. Those items that were freely accessible – around 16,000 – were made available through Library Search | Ketu. At the beginning of April 2025, these were also added to

Hākēna, thus achieving the goal of 'a minimum level of appropriate discovery, delivery and access'.

Due to donor agreements and copyright restrictions, some of the items (around 1,100) were made accessible only to people in the Hocken Reading Room. This phase took longer than expected due to technology constraints but was also delivered at the beginning of April 2025.

The access to these digital collection items by Library customers has been steadily growing. This is encouraging as there has been no external promotional push of the new service. People are discovering and accessing things organically.

The project team also created the workflows and deposit application to allow ingest digital collection items. Both have since been used to ingest items and metadata from the Marsden Online Archive, one of the Library's separate digital delivery services as well as digitisations of the 1925-1927 series of Critic Te Ārohi, the student magazine of the Otago University Students' Association on its 100th anniversary. This work has allowed us to test and adapt our techniques and technologies.

Potential migration of other Library standalone digital delivery systems will be investigated in the coming months.

Though the project managed to integrate Rosetta with the published collection management system, true integration with the unpublished collection management system was unachieved.

There has been an organisational turn towards digital preservation as an ongoing activity rather than a one-off task done at the end of a digitisation project. In addition to the forthcoming dedicated role to manage digital preservation, knowledge and ambassadorship in the digital preservation area has increased across the Library.

In addition, discussions have already begun about what other collections should be ingested into Rosetta. Digital theses and other research outputs, research data and local web harvests are being considered.

The coming years present the Library with further opportunities, potentially providing preservation as a service (PaaS) for the University. Other partnerships with ITS may come out of this as well, including an emulation platform for non-traditional research outputs that require preservation and long-term access.

The walk has begun; it's only a matter of time until we are running with digital preservation.

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